

A New Kind of Parity and Loschmidt's Paradox

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ABSTRACT

The conventional parity operation consists of the exchange of “right” and “left”, hence its alternative name, “mirror inversion”, since it is the one performed by common plane mirrors. Such specificity in the inversion surface, though, is pointed out in this paper as being responsible for its less fundamental character. Here, a new kind of parity is introduced, whose inversion surface is a general, *closed* one, and consists of the exchange of the inside and outside subspaces that the surface defines. It has been named “inside-out” inversion, or simply, space inversion, and encloses the conventional right-left parity as the particular case when the *inside* and *outside* are identical. As an example, Maxwell's equations in free space will be considered. This case is important since the time-reversible character of classical electromagnetism is under question due to the irreversible physical behaviour of radiation. For this case, both space and time inversions will be carried out and compared, and it will be shown that the electromagnetic field in free space is space-invariant, while it is not time-invariant, as commonly assumed.

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1. Introduction

The conventional parity conservation law, or mirror symmetry, used to establish — wrongly— that Nature is not able to distinguish the real world from its image in a mirror [1]. With hindsight, we realize the fragility of that principle. If we asked what kind of mirror would be able to perform that *fundamental* exchange, the answer would be “the plane ones”. Such specificity is the hint that the mirror inversion was not so fundamental, after all. Why precisely plane mirrors?

Indeed, the inversion surface for the right-left parity is a plane. But perfect plane surfaces do not exist in Nature. The kind of limitation in having a perfect plane is not only circumstantial, because of the technological impossibility of making perfect planes, without imperfections. Beyond that, the impossibility comes from a natural limit imposed by the curvature of space-time itself: It is well known that, despite the fact that space-time is almost euclidean (plane) everywhere, it suffers a bend in the vicinity of a black hole and/or a singularity (in general, in the vicinity of mass). The space-time bending is a fundamental limit in the possibilities of making, —and defining—, a plane surface at determined quantum and cosmic scales. The non-fundamental nature of the conventional parity becomes obvious in those regions where perfect zero curvature surfaces are not (and cannot) be defined.

Obviously, it can be replied that the “plane” for the mirror inversion is not a physical, but a mathematical object. Taken as such, a plane is geometrically a spherical surface of infinite radius, and hence, it is a very particular surface within a kind (of closed surfaces, in general), and the inversion with regard to it, a very particular inversion within a kind. Such a degree of specificity contrasts with the universality of natural laws. Why is so much specificity demanded for laws which, on the other hand, are supposed to be universal?

This paper introduces an extended concept of parity, which precisely relaxes the specificity of the conventional parity transformation. The new parity consists of the generalization of the inversion surface, now not a plane, but a general, *closed* one. The new parity establishes the symmetry of natural laws with regard to an exchange of the inside and outside subspaces that the surface defines. This generalization is based on the idea that a natural law should not be spatially bound: 1) its range of validity should be universal, not dying or ending at the boundary of an arbitrary region, and 2) the arbitrary surface should not modify the law, i.e., the law should not distinguish between

regions (otherwise, its validity would be spatially bound, against the premise). These conditions force the symmetry of the law with regard to any possible point of view of the observer: for any closed surface, natural laws should be symmetric (invariant) under the exchange of *inside* and *outside*. A good name for this symmetry could be “inside-out” parity, or simply, space parity.

The generalization of the inversion surface is not a mere generalization for no apparent reason. It is precisely motivated by the case of classical electromagnetism, since a closed surface is a geometrical boundary, able to enclose emitters (or receivers) of electromagnetic waves. Once emitted, the field crosses the surface in one determined direction: For the emitter inside (the receiver outside), the field *exits*, and reciprocally, for the receiver inside (the emitter outside), the field *enters*. Whichever is inside or outside, the reciprocity between emitter-receiver is the same as the one between inside-outside, disregarding their specific locations. The exchangeability of spaces is the key to the spatial reversibility of the electromagnetic flow. However, the field is not able to spontaneously change its flow-sense, as would be required for the field to be time-reversible¹. The aim of this paper is to extract that conclusion from Maxwell’s equations, against the orthodox view which defends the theoretical time reversibility of the electromagnetic field. But first, let us put in context that problem of classical electromagnetism with time-inversion.

1.1 Loschmidt’s paradox

It is well known that electromagnetic fields diverge from accelerated charges, while the opposite phenomenon of converging fields into accelerated charges has never been observed. This *arrow of radiation*, as it is called, seems to collapse with the apparent time-symmetry of Maxwell’s equations, commonly taken as fully time-reversible, since they do not seem to differentiate between retarded and advanced solutions. Nature, indeed, prefers the retarded solution over the advanced one, an asymmetry that does not fit into the proclaimed time-symmetry of Maxwell’s equations.

This disparity between theory and reality is called “Loschmidt’s paradox” [2]. Many authors have studied the question of where the time arrow is filtered into our electrodynamics equations. One of the most popular and well-known answers is the Wheeler-Feynman theory of *infinite absorbers* [3]. This theory postulates the need for “*absorbers*”, on one hand, (in order to cancel the advanced solution), which, on the other hand, need to be “*infinite*”, (in order to avoid the infinite contribution of the self-field of the accelerated charge to its own radiation, saving the renormalization problems associated with it). The problems with this theory are diverse: one is whether absorbers are really temporal inverters of emissions, a hypothesis which is needed so that the advanced solution can be perfectly cancelled. Also, there is the question of what happens in absence of absorbers (and sources), for instance, when the electromagnetic field propagates in free space, and why it behaves there as fully retarded. Another version of this theory was given by H. Price. In his book *Time’s arrow and Archimedes’ Point* and previous articles [4], he is convinced that it is just a matter of scale: the incoherence of the infinite absorbers at macroscopic level is just what makes the perfect

¹ That would require not a simple relocation emitter-receiver, but a *transmutation* of an emitter into a receiver and vice versa, with their locations unchanged.

cancellation of the advanced solution, —which for him actually exists—, impossible. Thus, the perfect symmetry on a microscopic scale, in his opinion, holds true, despite the macroscopic radiation arrow on a large scale. Another author, D. Zeh, insists on the absorbers idea, despite linking the definition of the ideal absorber to past macroscopic boundary conditions of space-time [5]. Following this line of argument is the article by J. North, who links the arrow of radiation to the macroscopic thermodynamic arrow of time [6]. With all due respect, this idea seems to me a bit dodgy: It deliberately places the origin of the macroscopic arrow far enough, so as not to have to worry about it: the unreachable (and untestable) initial conditions of the Universe —the so-called “Past Hypothesis”—. Approaches like these leave us with a strange feeling of dissatisfaction: their vagueness seems to be an emergency solution, rather than a real explanation in search of a genuine understanding of the matter. But even accepting this weak explanation as the origin of the asymmetry of radiation, a question is still left unanswered: if the behaviour of radiation is asymmetric, why then is classical electromagnetism time-symmetric?

It is remarkable that all the above-mentioned authors, in agreement with classic interpretations [7-8] have accepted beyond any doubt that classical electromagnetism is time-reversible, because of the fact that Maxwell’s equations “do not differentiate” between retarded and advanced solutions. With the exception of D. Albert [9], the possibility that Maxwell’s equations are actually *not* reversible in time has never been suggested. Even a different view, put forward by M. Frisch, maintains, like all the previous authors, that Maxwell’s equations are time-symmetric, and in order to match the observed asymmetry of radiation with the apparent symmetry of equations, he needs to “delimit what is physically possible”, by means of adding an additional condition, *the retardation condition*, on a basis of causality and real physical phenomenology [10].

In this paper, I question the main premise that classical electromagnetism is time-invariant, as commonly accepted. More specifically, the aim of this paper is to show that Maxwell’s equations in free space are not. But first, we need to understand what kind of reversibility they do fulfil. Starting with Maxwell’s static equations, this is dealt with in the next section.

2 Space symmetry in Maxwell’s equations

The conventional parity is the type of inversion performed by a plane mirror. Here we are interested in relaxing the inversion surface, to a general closed one, in order to define a more general parity concept. The idea is simply like turning a sock inside out: for a given surface, the space inversion consists of the exchange of one subspace for the other, the inside is treated as it was previously the outside, and vice versa. A function would be space-invariant if it stood unaltered after the space exchange. As the plane is a particular case of a closed surface, —which closes at the infinite—, it is obvious that the right-left parity is a particular case of space parity, where both subspaces are identical. For that reason, if a law is space-invariant, it must also be right-left invariant, but the opposite, in general, is not true.

Due to its generality, the application of this kind of inversion may not be so straightforward as the conventional one, unless the surface is explicitly involved in the

laws. That is the case of classical electromagnetism, at least with Gauss's equations, which are written in integral form in terms of an arbitrary closed surface S :

$$\oint_S \mathbf{E} \cdot d\mathbf{S} = \frac{q}{\epsilon_0} \quad (1.a)$$

$$\oint_S \mathbf{B} \cdot d\mathbf{S} = 0 \quad (1.b)$$

where q is the charge enclosed within, and $d\mathbf{S}$ is the surface vector pointing outwards, (see figure 1).

Figure 1: Conventional definition of the surface and circulation vectors at each point of a closed surface. The circulation vector $d\ell$ is contouring C in the indicated direction, according to the right-hand rule.

Let us distinguish with subscripts the two subspaces defined by the surface: subspace I is the inside, (shaded) and subspace O is the outside, (white). Let us call the charge within subspace I q_I , and correspondingly, the charge which belongs to subspace O, q_O . These are not independent: in this paper, both the charge conservation principle (i.e., the charge is neither created nor destroyed at any point of the Universe) and the charge neutrality of the Universe² are assumed. This means that, for any charge isolated within a surface, there must be the same amount of opposite charge somewhere outside the surface. Mathematically:

$$q_I = -q_O, \quad (2)$$

As we are interested in checking the reversibility of equations (1) with regard to the exchange of both subspaces, let us place two observers, one in the subspace I (observer I) and the other in the subspace O (observer O). Both are willing to formulate Maxwell's equations, for which they should adopt some kind of convention for defining the surface and circulation vectors. If they, for example, agreed in taking the surface

² The charge conservation principle establishes the constancy of the total net charge of the Universe, although its value is not specified. In this paper I follow the authors in [11-12] in taking it as zero, meaning the balance of positive and negative charge.

vector $d\mathbf{S}$ as pointing “outwards”, and defining the corresponding circulation vector at each point $d\ell$ as given by the right-hand rule, observer-I, from his point of view, would take this couple of vectors as being $d\mathbf{S}_I$ and $d\ell_I$ (figure 2.a), while observer-O, from his, would say that they are $d\mathbf{S}_O$ and $d\ell_O$ (figure 2.b).

As the outside of one is the inside of the other, note that

$$d\mathbf{S}_I \equiv -d\mathbf{S}_O \quad (3)$$

And the circulation vectors also verify:

$$d\ell_I \equiv -d\ell_O \quad (4)$$

With this notation, Gauss’s electric equation (1.a) takes the form:

$$\oint_S \mathbf{E} \cdot d\mathbf{S}_I = \frac{q_I}{\epsilon_0} \quad (5)$$

By using equations (2) and (3), in (5):

$$\oint_S \mathbf{E} \cdot d\mathbf{S}_I = \oint_S \mathbf{E} \cdot (-d\mathbf{S}_O) = \frac{q_I}{\epsilon_0} = -\frac{q_O}{\epsilon_0} \quad (6)$$

This leads to Gauss’s complementary law expression in terms of the O subspace:

$$\oint_S \mathbf{E} \cdot d\mathbf{S}_O = \frac{q_O}{\epsilon_0} \quad (7)$$

Note that it is formally identical to (5), meaning the symmetry of the law with regard to the inside-out exchange³.

For obvious reasons, Gauss’s magnetic law (1.b) is even more clearly symmetrical with regard to the space exchange. Let us now check the space inversion for Ampère and Faraday’s laws.

For the case of Maxwell’s time-dependent equations, only propagation in free space will be taken here into consideration, since radiation —whose time-behaviour is our goal—, is normally assumed as the specific case of the unguided transport of waves and energy through empty space. For reasons that will be apparent in the next section, the free-source terms have been here omitted on purpose, for the sake of simplicity, and also to

³ It is remarkable that the hypothesis of space symmetry of Maxwell’s equations has to assume the hypothesis of charge neutrality of the Universe. They need each other: reciprocally, the space symmetry of Maxwell’s equations could have been assumed beforehand, and taken to support the hypothesis of the charge neutrality of the Universe.

avoid contamination or mistakes coming from the conventional approach, (for the interested reader, the space reversibility of Ampère-Maxwell's, and the continuity equation, can be found in Appendix I). In free space, this is the way in which Ampère and Faraday's laws are written in integral form (natural units, the light velocity $c = 1$):

$$\oint_C \mathbf{B} \cdot d\ell = \frac{\partial \int_S \mathbf{E} \cdot d\mathbf{S}}{\partial t} \quad (8.a)$$

$$\oint_C \mathbf{E} \cdot d\ell = -\frac{\partial \int_S \mathbf{B} \cdot d\mathbf{S}}{\partial t} \quad (8.b)$$

The surface S in these equations is now open, (limited by the contour C , whose direction is linked to the surface vector according to the right-hand rule). Still, we can always take it as a part of a bigger, closed surface (a *window*). With this borrowed interpretation from the previous case, it makes sense to keep calling the orientation of $d\mathbf{S}$ as either inwards $d\mathbf{S}_O$, or outwards, $d\mathbf{S}_I$, the "cavity", (despite S , the window surface, being open), each one linked to its own circulating vector, $d\ell_I$ and $d\ell_O$. Like the previous ones, they also verify equations (3) and (4).

Figure 2: Definition of the surface and circulation vectors for (a) the inside (I-) and (b) outside (O-) subspaces. The circulation vectors $d\ell_I$ and $d\ell_O$ are respectively contouring C_I and C_O . Note that the I-vectors coincide with the conventional definition in figure 1.

With this notation, Ampère's law (8.a) can be rewritten in terms of the I-subspace as (natural units):

$$\oint_C \mathbf{B} \cdot d\ell_I = \frac{\partial \int_S \mathbf{E} \cdot d\mathbf{S}_I}{\partial t} \quad (9)$$

The question is whether or not we can write a similar equation in terms of the O-subspace. The answer is yes. By using equations (3) and (4), it is obvious that:

$$\frac{\partial \int_s \mathbf{E} \cdot d\mathbf{S}_I}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial \int_s \mathbf{E} \cdot (-d\mathbf{S}_O)}{\partial t} \quad (10)$$

And

$$\oint_C \mathbf{B} \cdot d\ell_I = \oint_C \mathbf{B} \cdot (-d\ell_O) \quad (11)$$

Therefore, an identical expression to (9) can be obtained for Ampère's law in terms of the O-subspace:

$$\oint_C \mathbf{B} \cdot d\ell_O = \frac{\partial \oint_s \mathbf{E} \cdot d\mathbf{S}_O}{\partial t} \quad (12)$$

The same derivation can be made for Faraday's law (8.b). Maxwell's free-space equations, to sum up, stand on a spatial boundary S:

Spatial Boundary (I ↔ O)	
Subspace I	Subspace O
$\oint_C \mathbf{B} \cdot d\ell_I = \frac{\partial \int_s \mathbf{E} \cdot d\mathbf{S}_I}{\partial t}$	$\oint_C \mathbf{B} \cdot d\ell_O = \frac{\partial \int_s \mathbf{E} \cdot d\mathbf{S}_O}{\partial t}$
$\oint_C \mathbf{E} \cdot d\ell_I = -\frac{\partial \int_s \mathbf{B} \cdot d\mathbf{S}_I}{\partial t}$	$\oint_C \mathbf{E} \cdot d\ell_O = -\frac{\partial \int_s \mathbf{B} \cdot d\mathbf{S}_O}{\partial t}$

Note that this kind of inversion is *spatial* (time has been untouched in it). The symmetry of the laws relative to the space-exchange is obvious: The electromagnetic field, *such as we know it*, can either *enter* or *exit* a closed surface, since the equations that govern it do not distinguish between inside and outside. This, which may seem a triviality, will not seem so when compared with the different behaviour of the electromagnetic field at a temporal boundary. This will be dealt with in the next section.

3. Time symmetry in Maxwell's equations

Let me start this section with an inspiring paragraph by Sakurai [13]:

*In this section, we study another discrete symmetry operator, called **time reversal**. This is a difficult topic for the novice, partly because the term *time reversal* is a misnomer (...). Actually, what we do in this section can be more appropriately characterized by the term reversal of motion. Indeed, that is the terminology used by E. Wigner, who formulated time reversal in a very fundamental paper written in 1932.*

The paper Sakurai is talking about is [14]. This piece suggests that the electromagnetic field has been commonly viewed in purely *mechanistic* terms: its behaviour in time is subordinated to the behaviour of the charge in motion [15].

This subordination implies a particular way to solve Maxwell's equations with the time backwards. That way consists in reassigning the minus coming from the time backwards to one of the fields, —which usually is the magnetic field [16]. So the approach in the textbooks for the time inversion lies in the substitution of \mathbf{B} by $-\mathbf{B}$ in Maxwell's equations, considering the *effect* that a charge moving backwards would produce on the magnetic field. Still, there is another approach by Feynman, which, instead, reassigns the minus coming from the time backwards to the electric field, (i.e., \mathbf{E} is replaced by $-\mathbf{E}$ in Maxwell's equations), now considering the *cause*, i.e., the fact that, for a charge to reverse its motion, it would require a reversed electric field. Both approaches are complementary and mutually-excluding. This exclusion is the seed of their incorrectness: both are possibly right, so none of them can be, since the one's success implies the failure of the other. Correctness is compromised in the dilemma of choosing between cause or effect, indissolubly connected by the time-link we are looking for.

Leaving interpretations aside, if for the time reversal we need to take on board \mathbf{B} by $-\mathbf{B}$ (or \mathbf{E} by $-\mathbf{E}$) in Maxwell's equations, this means that, strictly speaking, we are not solving Maxwell's equations: we are solving Maxwell's equations *plus a condition* in the field. We are therefore *driving* the solution, on the basis of what we think the time reversal might be, —a perception that may be wrong if the time reversal is more extraordinary than expected.—.

In either case, Maxwell's equations with the time backwards become identical to the time forwards set, (and their solutions, obviously, too), so the electromagnetic field with the time backwards turns out to be the same as the one with the time forwards, (except for a phase shift), which makes inexplicable why then it is not observed, if it is so real.

These conventional approaches are based on that single principle, —I would rather say a *prejudice*—, which considers matter the prime reality, and the field, secondary (in Wigner's own words [1]). At least we have to concede that there exists another way to focus the problem: to invert the importance of matter and field, and consider matter as the subordinated reality, and the field, the prime one. That is the new approach explored in this paper.

3.1 Comparison between time-backwards and forwards: The double symmetry

If matter is not relevant for learning the time behaviour of radiation, we can take it away from the equations, and restrict our analysis to Maxwell's equations *in empty space*. Time running forwards makes the passing of time Δt positive, and running backwards, negative. This has been taken into account with the following notation:

$$\Delta t = \begin{cases} \Delta |t| & \Delta t > 0 \\ -\Delta |t| & \Delta t < 0 \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

For a better comparison, let us write both Maxwell's sets, forwards and backwards, together. In terms of the I-subspace⁴, since it is identical to the convention, and in natural units, (the light velocity $c=1$):

Temporal Boundary ($t \rightarrow -t$)

t (forwards) \rightarrow	$\leftarrow t$ (backwards)
$\oint_{\mathbf{c}} \mathbf{B} \cdot d\ell_{\mathbf{I}} = \frac{\partial \int_{\mathbf{s}} \mathbf{E} \cdot d\mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{I}}}{\partial t } \quad (14.a)$	$\oint_{\mathbf{c}} \mathbf{B} \cdot d\ell_{\mathbf{I}} = -\frac{\partial \int_{\mathbf{s}} \mathbf{E} \cdot d\mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{I}}}{\partial t } \quad (15.a)$
$\oint_{\mathbf{c}} \mathbf{E} \cdot d\ell_{\mathbf{I}} = -\frac{\partial \int_{\mathbf{s}} \mathbf{B} \cdot d\mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{I}}}{\partial t } \quad (14.b)$	$\oint_{\mathbf{c}} \mathbf{E} \cdot d\ell_{\mathbf{I}} = \frac{\partial \int_{\mathbf{s}} \mathbf{B} \cdot d\mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{I}}}{\partial t } \quad (15.b)$

Set (14) in the left is the usual t -forward, while set (15) in the right is the time-inverted set. We can get rid of the explicit minus in equations (14.b) and (15.a) by means of equation (3):

t (forwards) \rightarrow	$\leftarrow t$ (backwards)
$\oint_{\mathbf{c}} \mathbf{B} \cdot d\ell_{\mathbf{I}} = \frac{\partial \int_{\mathbf{s}} \mathbf{E} \cdot d\mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{I}}}{\partial t } \quad (16.a)$	$\oint_{\mathbf{c}} \mathbf{B} \cdot d\ell_{\mathbf{I}} = \frac{\partial \int_{\mathbf{s}} \mathbf{E} \cdot d\mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{O}}}{\partial t } \quad (17.a)$
$\oint_{\mathbf{c}} \mathbf{E} \cdot d\ell_{\mathbf{I}} = \frac{\partial \int_{\mathbf{s}} \mathbf{B} \cdot d\mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{O}}}{\partial t } \quad (16.b)$	$\oint_{\mathbf{c}} \mathbf{E} \cdot d\ell_{\mathbf{I}} = \frac{\partial \int_{\mathbf{s}} \mathbf{B} \cdot d\mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{I}}}{\partial t } \quad (17.b)$

⁴ It is not necessary the inside-out notation in this case, (see for instance [15], in terms of right and left). I have used it here for keeping the parallelism with the space inversion, and highlighting the difference between both cases.

Clearly, equations sets (16) and (17) are of opposite handedness: In (16.a), $d\ell_{\mathbf{I}}$ is linked to $d\mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{I}}$, so it is *right*-handed (surface and contour are linked by the right-hand rule). In (16.b), $d\ell_{\mathbf{I}}$ is linked to $d\mathbf{S}_{\mathbf{O}}$, thus it is *left*-handed (surface and contour are linked by the left-hand rule). Set (17) is the mirrored set (16), if we just allow a change of handedness in the contour-surface link: equations (16.a) and (17.a) are respectively the right and left versions of the same equation, and so are equations (16.b) and (17.b), the left and right versions of the same relation between \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} . Actually the four are all the very same equation, if we just allow the exchange of handedness $Right \leftrightarrow Left$ and fields $\mathbf{E} \leftrightarrow \mathbf{B}$.

This way of writing both sets reveals the hidden symmetry between them. Neither of them seems more special than the other. If we accept no conditions in the fields for set (16), we have no right to deny the same status (condition-free) to set (17), or otherwise, we would be deliberately breaking the symmetry, by favouring one set over the other.

Now both sets are not reversible, against the general opinion, but the symmetry between them is *double*: one Maxwell's set becomes the other either if we perform an exchange of *handedness*, (here called "**H**-symmetry"), or equivalently, an exchange of *fields* ("**F**-symmetry"). By means of simple algebraic relationships, both transformations can be checked to be equivalent. By direct comparison with the time-forwards wave, the time-backwards wave can be easily obtained. Obviously, the two waves must reproduce the same double symmetry of the equations they come from. For the simplest case of a plane wave, this is illustrated in the next section.

3.2 Electromagnetic Plane Waves at a Temporal Boundary

It has been shown the double time-symmetry of Maxwell's equations. Let us explore now the *solutions*, considering the simplest far-field case in lossless media, where the field becomes a plane wave and Maxwell's equations turn into a simple set of algebraic equations. As a reference, let us recall the usual time-forward set, which is written in this case as follows (natural units):

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
& t \text{ (forwards)} \rightarrow & \\
\hat{\mathbf{k}} \cdot \mathbf{E} = 0 & & \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{E} = \mathbf{B} \\
& & \\
\hat{\mathbf{k}} \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0 & & \hat{\mathbf{k}} \times \mathbf{B} = -\mathbf{E}
\end{array} \tag{18}$$

where $\frac{|\mathbf{E}|}{|\mathbf{B}|} = 1$, and the cross product is given, as usual, by the right hand rule.

3.2.1 Exchange of handedness

If the exchange of handedness is performed in equations (18), the t-backward set is obtained. For a better comparison, let us write them together:

$t \text{ (forwards)} \rightarrow$	Temporal Boundary	$\leftarrow t \text{ (backwards)}$
$\hat{\mathbf{k}}_+ \cdot \mathbf{E}_+ = 0$		$\hat{\mathbf{k}}_- \cdot \mathbf{E}_- = 0$
$\hat{\mathbf{k}}_+ \cdot \mathbf{B}_+ = 0$		$\hat{\mathbf{k}}_- \cdot \mathbf{B}_- = 0$
$\hat{\mathbf{k}}_+ \times_{\mathbf{R}} \mathbf{E}_+ = \mathbf{B}_+ \tag{19}$		$\hat{\mathbf{k}}_- \times_{\mathbf{L}} \mathbf{E}_- = \mathbf{B}_- \tag{20}$
$\hat{\mathbf{k}}_+ \times_{\mathbf{R}} \mathbf{B}_+ = -\mathbf{E}_+$		$\hat{\mathbf{k}}_- \times_{\mathbf{L}} \mathbf{B}_- = -\mathbf{E}_-$

The subscripts + and - underline the domains, t -forwards or backwards, for which they are defined. Here, again, $\frac{|\mathbf{E}|}{|\mathbf{B}|} = 1$, for both (19) and (20), and $\hat{\mathbf{k}}_+$ and $\hat{\mathbf{k}}_-$ are the direction vectors of the $t+$ and $t-$ waves, with

$$\hat{\mathbf{k}}_+ = -\hat{\mathbf{k}}_-, \tag{21}$$

so that the $t+$ and $t-$ waves have opposite directions.

Note that the handedness is only involved in the cross products, so they now need to be distinguished, $\times_{\mathbf{R}}$ right- and $\times_{\mathbf{L}}$ left-handed. For set (19), the right-hand is usually adopted, and so it has been kept here, —the cross product $\times_{\mathbf{R}}$ in (19) is identical to the usual cross product \times in (18) —, while $\times_{\mathbf{L}}$ in (20) is defined in Appendix II.

A solution compatible with both sets and with equation (21) is shown in figure 3: the two versions, right- and left, of the same electromagnetic field arise at each side of the

boundary. The t-forward wave $\{\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{B}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}_+\}_R$ forms a right-hand triad, and subsequently the t-backward wave must be the left-hand triad⁵, $\{\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{B}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}_-\}_L$

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \leftarrow \mathbf{t} \text{ (back)} & | & \mathbf{t} \text{ (forw)} \rightarrow \\ \mathbf{E} \times_L \mathbf{B} & & \mathbf{E} \times_R \mathbf{B} \end{array} \quad (22)$$

At the t-boundary itself,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{E}_+ &= \mathbf{E}_- \Big|_{t=0} \\ \mathbf{B}_+ &= \mathbf{B}_- \Big|_{t=0} \\ \hat{\mathbf{k}}_+ &= -\hat{\mathbf{k}}_- \Big|_{t=0} \end{aligned}$$

“ $t=0$ ” represents here the “time-zero”, or temporal boundary, which, as this result suggests, cannot be considered a mere, arbitrary selection of our timer. On the contrary, it is a highly extraordinary circumstance where the field would perform an extraordinary change of handedness, never so far observed (see section 6).

Note that the handedness symmetry between the equations (19) and (20), is fully passed on to the solutions (22), with no need for further conditions or considerations about how we imagine the time-backward field might be. As shown in figure 3, the effect of a temporal boundary is to mirror the field, instead of mirroring the charge motion⁶.

Figure 3: The two, t-forward and t-backward, waves, emerge at both sides of a t-boundary with the opposite handedness. The t-forward wave is the conventional electromagnetic wave, i.e., the right-hand triad $\mathbf{E}\mathbf{B}\mathbf{k}$. The symbols R and L stand for *right* and *left*, and represent the advance of a right- or left- screw.

It is interesting to recall that the handedness convention is arbitrary, which always allows for a definition of the field in two alternative forms, right or left, depending on

⁵ With time forwards, \mathbf{E} rotates towards \mathbf{B} according to a right-hand screw which advances to the $\hat{\mathbf{k}}_+$ -direction. With time backwards, \mathbf{E} rotates towards \mathbf{B} according to a left-handed screw, which points to the $\hat{\mathbf{k}}_-$ -direction.

⁶ This different result comes from the essentially different approach: the conventional one adopts the charge motion as “the prime reality”, and the field is subordinated to it [14]. For this paper’s, the charge is not even involved: the prime reality is the field [15].

the convention used: for the t -forwards, for example, the use of the *right-hand* is generalised, and hence the use of the $\{\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{B}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}_+\}_R$ triad, but it would also be possible to have used the opposite, left handedness, with which the field would be equally defined by the *left-handed triad* $\{\mathbf{B}, \mathbf{E}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}_+\}_L$. Identically, for the t -backwards, the above-mentioned left-handed triad $\{\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{B}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}_-\}_L$, or alternatively, the $\{\mathbf{B}, \mathbf{E}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}_+\}_R$ right-handed one, equally represent the t -backward field, by virtue of the simple algebraic relations between both handedness types (see Appendix II). This allows us to rewrite (22) in any of the following forms:

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 & \text{Temporal Boundary} & \\
 \leftarrow t \text{ (backwards)} & & t \text{ (forwards)} \rightarrow \\
 \mathbf{E} \times_L \mathbf{B} = -\mathbf{B} \times_L \mathbf{E} = \mathbf{B} \times_R \mathbf{E} & \Big| & \mathbf{E} \times_R \mathbf{B} = -\mathbf{B} \times_R \mathbf{E} = \mathbf{B} \times_L \mathbf{E} \\
 \text{(23.a)} & & \text{(23.b)}
 \end{array}$$

As expected, the double symmetry of the equations is also fulfilled by the solution:

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 & \text{Temporal Boundary} & \\
 \leftarrow t \text{ (backwards)} & & t \text{ (forwards)} \rightarrow \\
 & \text{F-symmetry} & \\
 \mathbf{E} \times_L \mathbf{B} = \mathbf{B} \times_R \mathbf{E} & & \mathbf{B} \times_L \mathbf{E} = \mathbf{E} \times_R \mathbf{B} \\
 & \text{H-symmetry} &
 \end{array}$$

where \mathbf{H} stands for Handedness symmetry (right-left) $\mathbf{R} \leftrightarrow \mathbf{L}$, and \mathbf{F} stands for Field symmetry, $\mathbf{E} \leftrightarrow \mathbf{B}$. We have reached this by performing the first operation \mathbf{H} . Obviously, the same result should be obtained after the second one \mathbf{F} , since they are equivalent.

3.2.2 Exchange of fields

Equally, the t -forward set (16) turns into the t -backward set (17), by performing an exchange of fields $\mathbf{E} \leftrightarrow \mathbf{B}$. Both sets are formally identical, with \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} renamed. As it is obvious that mathematics do not penalize the name-exchange, the plane-wave t -backward set must be formally identical to (19), with \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} renamed:

$$\begin{aligned}
& t \text{ (forwards)} \rightarrow \\
& \hat{\mathbf{k}}_+ \cdot \mathbf{E}_+ = 0 \\
& \hat{\mathbf{k}}_+ \cdot \mathbf{B}_+ = 0 \\
& \hat{\mathbf{k}}_+ \times_R \mathbf{E}_+ = \mathbf{B}_+ \\
& \hat{\mathbf{k}}_+ \times_R \mathbf{B}_+ = -\mathbf{E}_+
\end{aligned} \tag{24.a}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \leftarrow t \text{ (backwards)} \\
& \hat{\mathbf{k}}_- \cdot \mathbf{B}_- = 0 \\
& \hat{\mathbf{k}}_- \cdot \mathbf{E}_- = 0 \\
& \hat{\mathbf{k}}_- \times_R \mathbf{B}_- = \mathbf{E}_- \\
& \hat{\mathbf{k}}_- \times_R \mathbf{E}_- = -\mathbf{B}_-
\end{aligned} \tag{24.b}$$

where $\frac{|\mathbf{E}_+|}{|\mathbf{B}_+|} = 1$

and $\frac{|\mathbf{B}_-|}{|\mathbf{E}_-|} = 1$

Again, subscripts + and – highlight t -directions, (despite being clear in the top line of the equations). Note that all the cross products are now right-handed, since the handedness, in this case, has not been modified. For the t -forward set (24.a), the field is the (*right-hand*) $\{\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{B}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}_+\}_R$ triad, and so the t -backward field must be the (also *right-hand*) $\{\mathbf{B}, \mathbf{E}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}_-\}_R$ triad (with vectors \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} exchanged). As expected, this result was already obtained —equation (23)—, and shown in figure 3. The t -backward field, $\{\mathbf{B}, \mathbf{E}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}_-\}_R$ is the *dual* of the t -forward field, $\{\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{B}, \hat{\mathbf{k}}_+\}_R$. The term “dual” is not arbitrary: it is borrowed from tensor analysis, with the same meaning⁷, (see section 4). Hence, the “electromagnetic” field going backwards in time is actually a “*magnetolectric*” field, or let us call it, the *dual electromagnetic* field, which is composed of the dual electric (the former \mathbf{B}) and the dual magnetic (the former \mathbf{E}). They have been indicated with apostrophes (figure 4):

Temporal Boundary

$$\begin{aligned}
& \leftarrow \mathbf{t} \text{ (backwards)} \\
& \mathbf{E} \times_L \mathbf{B} = \mathbf{B} \times_R \mathbf{E} = \mathbf{E}' \times_R \mathbf{B}' \\
& \tag{25.a}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathbf{t} \text{ (forwards)} \rightarrow \\
& \mathbf{E} \times_R \mathbf{B} = \mathbf{B} \times_L \mathbf{E} = \mathbf{E}' \times_L \mathbf{B}' \\
& \tag{25.b}
\end{aligned}$$

At the t -boundary, they fulfil:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{E}_+ &= \mathbf{B}'_- \Big|_{t=0} \\
\mathbf{B}_+ &= \mathbf{E}'_- \Big|_{t=0} \\
\hat{\mathbf{k}}_+ &= -\hat{\mathbf{k}}_- \Big|_{t=0}
\end{aligned}$$

⁷ The dual tensor is the resulting field tensor, after the field exchange, (see Appendix III).

With this notation, the symmetry of the solution is overwhelming: the electromagnetic field could be defined, either by the conventional wave, or by its dual, with the opposite handedness. At the temporal boundary, the field just transforms into its dual (I will recall this result in section 4):

It is paradoxical that, contrary to what happens with space inversion, Maxwell's equations (and their solutions) are not time-invariant because they do distinguish between $t+$ and $t-$. And yet, they are double-symmetric (anti-symmetric, actually). The apparent asymmetry of radiation we observe in Nature, surprisingly seems to come from a *double symmetry*, if only we unfold the time dimension, in the two, backward and forward, directions.

Figure 4: Field time-symmetry, in terms of the dual fields, which have been identified with apostrophes. Again, the symbols R and L stand for *right* and *left*, and represent the advance of a right- or left- screw.

3.3 Comparison of space and time inversions

If we compare how Maxwell's equations transform in spatial and time inversions, we find an essential difference between the two cases: from the final equations in section 2, it is clear that Maxwell's equations do not change in a spatial inversion, while they do in a time inversion, if we just have a look at equations sets (16) and (17) in section 3. From the point of view of the electromagnetic field, one subspace is identical to the other. The directions of time, though, are not. Mathematically, the space inversion maintains the handedness, whichever it is, (*even* H-symmetry), while the time inversion does not (*odd* H-symmetry). Physically, this means that the locations of sources and sinks are exchangeable, but the transmutation of sources into sinks and vice versa, would require a mirror image of the conventional electromagnetic wave [15]. Such a behaviour has not

been observed so far in Nature, which may indicate, either that the electromagnetic field is not able to revert in time, (contrary to what is usually assumed), or, if it is so, that time boundaries are hardly accessible (see section 6).

4. Four-dimensional formulation

The four-dimensional formulation has been also used to justify the invariance of classical electromagnetism [17]. Indeed, if one starts from the same hypothesis (the identification of the field time reversal with the charge motion reversal), obviously will get the same result, expectedly invariant, with any of both formulations, classical or four-dimensional, since they are equivalent. The way in which the conventional time inversion ($\mathbf{B} \xrightarrow{T} -\mathbf{B}$) can be translated into the latter formulation:

$$F_{\mu\nu} \xrightarrow{T} F^{\mu\nu} \quad \text{(Conventional)}$$

$$F^{\mu\nu} \xrightarrow{T} F_{\mu\nu}$$

i.e., the Maxwell-Faraday tensor transforms into *its contravariant form* (see Appendix III). This makes the quantity $\frac{1}{2} F_{\mu\nu} F^{\mu\nu}$,—which is an invariant of electromagnetism—, to stand in the time inversion, since its value is given by (natural units):

$$\frac{1}{2} F_{\mu\nu} F^{\mu\nu} = B^2 - E^2$$

and obviously, it does not change under a sign flip, since the fields are squared. This is the way in which the four-dimensional formulation seems to confirm the premise of electromagnetic invariance under a time inversion. The difference is found, though, if we start from a *different* premise: if the time inversion is taken, not as the sign-flip

$\mathbf{B} \xrightarrow{T} -\mathbf{B}$, but as the one proposed here, $\mathbf{E} \xleftarrow{T} \mathbf{B}$, the correct tensor transformation would be:

$$F_{\mu\nu} \xrightarrow{T} G^{\mu\nu}$$

(this proposal)

$$F^{\mu\nu} \xrightarrow{T} G_{\mu\nu}$$

i.e., the Maxwell-Faraday tensor turns into *its dual*, —a result which is a natural extension of the one already obtained in the previous section 3.2.2. With this, the quantity $\frac{1}{2} F_{\mu\nu} F^{\mu\nu}$ does not hold any longer: Its value, $\frac{1}{2} F_{\mu\nu} F^{\mu\nu} = B^2 - E^2$, turns into:

$$\frac{1}{2} F_{\mu\nu} F^{\mu\nu} \xrightarrow{T} \frac{1}{2} G^{\mu\nu} G_{\mu\nu} = E^2 - B^2$$

i.e., *its sign flips*⁸, (just applying the exchange of fields to the standard value). If this is correct, the variability of the quantity $\frac{1}{2} F_{\mu\nu} F^{\mu\nu}$, otherwise invariant, may be another symptom that the electromagnetic field is indeed sensitive to time inversions, contrary to the common opinion.

5. Discussion of the solution

As put forward in section 3, Maxwell's equations with time backwards (15) are normally solved by reassigning the negative sign coming from time backwards to one of the fields. We find in literature two options [16]:

1. The textbook approach, which reassigns time's minus to the \mathbf{B} field (while \mathbf{E} does not change):

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{B} &\xrightarrow{T} -\mathbf{B} \\ (\mathbf{E} &\xrightarrow{T} \mathbf{E}) \end{aligned}$$

2. The alternative, Feynman's approach, which reassigns time's minus sign to the \mathbf{E} field (while \mathbf{B} does not change):

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{E} &\xrightarrow{T} -\mathbf{E} \\ (\mathbf{B} &\xrightarrow{T} \mathbf{B}) \end{aligned}$$

⁸ Under the conventional time inversion, this quantity behaves as a proper scalar. Under this paper's, it behaves as a pseudo scalar. This sign flip will also affect the electromagnetic Lagrangian with time backwards.

The textbook approach considers the *effect* that a charge moving backwards would produce on the magnetic field. Feynman's, instead, considers the *cause*, i.e., the fact that, for a charge to reverse its motion, it would require a reversed electric field.

The time inversion proposed in this paper does not mean any sign flip in the fields, but an *exchange of roles* between the electric and magnetic fields themselves⁹:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{E} &\overset{\mathbf{T}}{\longleftrightarrow} \mathbf{B} \\ \mathbf{B} &\overset{\mathbf{T}}{\longleftrightarrow} \mathbf{E} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{in natural units})$$

It is possible to justify this result, in comparison with the abovementioned approaches. Basically, the time backwards alters the normal sequence of events, and the cause-effect sequence is also inverted. With time forwards, the electric field (the cause) produces the charge motion, which, at the same time, produces the magnetic field (the effect). With time backwards the opposite is expected: the magnetic field (the effect) “counter-produces” the charge motion reversal (remember, with time backwards), which, at the same time “counter-produces” the electric field (the cause). With this new viewpoint, the exchange of roles between \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} would somehow be justified because, with time backwards, the effect (\mathbf{B}) is *prior* to the cause (\mathbf{E}), and responsible for the charge motion¹⁰.

$t \rightarrow$ forwards		$t \leftarrow$ backwards
cause \Rightarrow effect		cause \Leftarrow effect
$\mathbf{E} \Rightarrow$ motion charge $\Rightarrow \mathbf{B}$		$\mathbf{E} \Leftarrow$ motion charge $\Leftarrow \mathbf{B}$

6. But what is a time border?

For the conventional time-inversion, a time border would just be when the magnetic field suffers a phase shift $\mathbf{B} \rightarrow -\mathbf{B}$, crossing its zero-value (something relatively common, so much that anyone could force that event to happen any time) For this paper's, time borders are not such a common event, and of course not any arbitrary choice of our timer. Instead, they would be extraordinary time points where the electromagnetic field suffers an extraordinary exchange of roles, implying at the border itself the degeneracy of the electric and magnetic fields $\mathbf{E}=\mathbf{B}$. Indeed, they would be exceptional events, able to provide an absolute reference for the dimension of time, if measured or defined in relation to them.

⁹ The double symmetry should not be mistaken with the electric-magnetic duality, by means of which $\mathbf{E} \rightarrow \mathbf{B}$ and $\mathbf{B} \rightarrow -\mathbf{E}$, leaving Maxwell's equations invariant [18]. Being so, the two directions of time are indistinguishable, something which fulminates any hope of hosting time singularities, such as, for instance, the origin of the time arrow. The double symmetry precisely reveals how Maxwell's equations can discriminate the two directions of time, allowing that possibility.

¹⁰ This would mean that the electric and magnetic fields would be the temporal mirror of each other.

Such time points, in my view, would be more in line with true time borders already predicted in Cosmology, like the Big Bang or the absolute zero temperature. These two points are good time-border candidates, not only for the obvious cosmological reason of *End* and *Beginning* of Time they represent, but also for some phenomenology that has been predicted for them.

6.1 The absolute zero-point temperature

Regarding the temperature of absolute zero (0 K), precisely its impossibility to be achieved (according to the Third Law) suggests the same impossibility of going over the limit of time backwards. In the vicinity of that point, time just slows down, as we see, for instance, in the case of vital processes as temperature decreases. But there is a clue which may support this idea in a more concrete way. Wu's famous experiment, where parity breaks down, is performed just above (very near) the temperature of absolute zero [19]. That could be precisely the key factor: near absolute zero the fields unexpectedly degenerate, and the applied \mathbf{B} starts to behave like an electric field, provoking the exit of electrons in its opposite direction, *just as an electric field would do* (\mathbf{B} 's behaviour, though, would not be perfectly electric, but a degenerate magnetic-electric mixture).

It is remarkable that, in that famous experiment where parity breaks down, left and right start to become distinguishable, at the same time that the electric and magnetic fields start to degenerate (and vice versa: far from the border, when \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} are distinguishable, left and right degenerate). This indicates an intimate, balanced relationship between space and time, so far unexplained.

6.2 The Big Bang

The well-known “problem of the missing monopoles”, which arises from the prediction of the GUTs¹¹ in relation to an abundance of magnetic monopoles in the Big Bang, however, does not match with the fact of their inexistence now [18,20-21]. Despite being partially solved by the hypothesis of inflation, this problem could be also explained as a consequence of the field degeneracy at a time border.

Although the study of the charge behaviour is beyond the scope of this paper, note that the degeneracy of the fields at a time border implies the degeneracy of the monopoles, too. For the sake of economy of resources and symmetry, it can be deduced that two different kinds of monopoles (electric *and* magnetic) would be redundant *for a single kind of field* —the degenerated one— at the time border. The apparent distinction between the two kinds of monopoles would come from the field duality, electric-magnetic, which rules on each side. The distinction, therefore, would be rhetorical: there would not be “electric monopoles” or “magnetic monopoles”, but just “monopoles”, driven by electric and/or magnetic fields, depending on which side of the boundary are being observed from. At the time border itself, they would not be distinguishable, —just like the fields—. Thus, it would not be surprising a massive presence of “magnetic” monopoles at the Big Bang, (as well as “electric”): If the hypothesis in this paper is correct, they might be all the same at the time border, and their “mysterious”

¹¹ Grand Unified Theory.

disappearance afterwards would be the consequence of the ceasing of the field degeneracy, which makes them appear like “electric” monopoles from this side, quite far from the time border. The asymmetry of matter, (represented by the mentioned asymmetry of monopoles) would therefore be linked to the asymmetry of radiation, being both only apparent, consequence of the partial viewpoint from only one side of the time border.

6.3 Remarks on energy

The solution proposed in this paper suggests two waves (one at each side of the time border) which only differ in the handedness. If energy conservation is not a matter of handedness, the left-handed wave will fulfil energy conservation for time backwards, as much—or as less—as the right-handed one does, for time forwards. This, again, suggests the exceptionality of a time border, as a singular point where energy flips its sign (however, not so singular as to violate energy conservation, if the energy in both time directions keeps constant, see Appendix IV for further comments).

7. Conclusions

This paper deals with the problem of space and time inversions in classical electromagnetism. The space inversion in this paper is not the conventional right-left parity, but a generalization, in the sense that the inversion surface is not a plane, but a general, *closed* surface. The surface generalization is precisely motivated by our aim to explore the behaviour of classical electromagnetism in time, conventionally considered as time-reversible, due to a questionable *mechanistic* view of the electromagnetic field.

Here it has been shown that Maxwell’s equations in free space are space-invariant, but, contrary to the general opinion, they are not time-invariant, once released the hypothesis of subordination of the field to matter. Still, they show an overwhelming *double symmetry*, handedness (**H**-symmetry) and fields (**F**-symmetry). This symmetry pattern that the field shows in time suggests that the turning points of time (here called “time borders”) are not common nor arbitrary, but exceptional time points where the electromagnetic field performs an extraordinary exchange of roles, becoming degenerated at the border itself. This degeneracy has consequences on the number of monopoles required for the symmetry of classical electromagnetism, since it is redundant to define two different kinds of monopoles *for a single kind of field* (the degenerated one existing at the border). The asymmetry of matter and the asymmetry of radiation are both linked, being only apparent, consequence of the partial viewpoint from one side of the time border.

The behaviour of matter in time has been left unsolved in this paper. Not as obvious as a simple backwards motion, it would imply the redefinition of monopoles under the new field, and will have to be inferred from the time-symmetry demanded by the field. It could be a nice topic for the future.

Appendix I: Space reversibility of Ampère-Maxwell's equation, and the continuity equation

If we consider the notation I and O introduced in section 3, Ampère-Maxwell's equation can be written in terms of subspace I, as:

$$\oint_C \mathbf{B} \cdot d\ell_I = \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial \int_S \mathbf{E} \cdot d\mathbf{S}_I}{\partial t} + \mu_0 \int_S \mathbf{j} \cdot d\mathbf{S}_I$$

In terms of subspace O, it could be written as:

$$\oint_C \mathbf{B} \cdot d\ell_O = \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial \int_S \mathbf{E} \cdot d\mathbf{S}_O}{\partial t} + \mu_0 \int_S \mathbf{j} \cdot d\mathbf{S}_O$$

Obviously, both expressions are identical, by virtue of equations (3) and (4).

The same derivation can be done for the continuity equation. Observer I would write it as:

$$\int_S \mathbf{j} \cdot d\mathbf{S}_I = -\frac{dq_I}{dt}$$

Taking the derivative of equation of equation (2), $dq_I = -dq_O$, the same continuity equation also stands for observer O:

$$\int_S \mathbf{j} \cdot d\mathbf{S}_O = -\frac{dq_O}{dt}$$

This means that none of both points of view is preferred or more special than the other: there is a total symmetry between the *inside* and *outside* for Maxwell's equations.

Appendix II: Handedness in the vector product

A curious property of the cross product is that it is anti-commutative for same handedness,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{A} \times_R \mathbf{B} &= -\mathbf{B} \times_R \mathbf{A}, \\ \mathbf{A} \times_L \mathbf{B} &= -\mathbf{B} \times_L \mathbf{A} \end{aligned}$$

and commutative for *opposite* handedness:

$$\mathbf{A} \times_R \mathbf{B} = \mathbf{B} \times_L \mathbf{A},$$

$$\mathbf{A} \times_L \mathbf{B} = \mathbf{B} \times_R \mathbf{A}$$

The right cross product \times_R is the conventional cross product \times , based on the right handed system, $\{\mathbf{u}_x, \mathbf{u}_y, \mathbf{u}_{z+}\}$. The left product \times_L is based on the mirror image of the right handed system, $\{\mathbf{u}_x, \mathbf{u}_y, \mathbf{u}_{z-}\}$:

$$\mathbf{A} \times_L \mathbf{B} = \begin{vmatrix} \mathbf{u}_x & \mathbf{u}_y & \mathbf{u}_{z-} \\ a_x & a_y & a_{z-} \\ b_x & b_y & b_{z-} \end{vmatrix}$$

where $\mathbf{u}_{z-} = -\mathbf{u}_{z+}$, and $\{a_x, a_y, a_{z-}\}$ and $\{b_x, b_y, b_{z-}\}$ are respectively the components of \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} in the left-handed system.

Appendix III: Notation for the four dimension formulation

The Maxwell-Faraday tensor $F_{\mu\nu}$ is given by [22]:

$$F_{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -cB_z & +cB_y & -E_x \\ +cB_z & 0 & -cB_x & -E_y \\ -cB_y & +cB_x & 0 & -E_z \\ +E_x & +E_y & +E_z & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

And the contravariant form, $F^{\mu\nu}$:

$$F^{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -cB_z & +cB_y & +E_x \\ +cB_z & 0 & -cB_x & +E_y \\ -cB_y & +cB_x & 0 & +E_z \\ -E_x & -E_y & -E_z & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Note that both are related by one field's sign flip, which represents the conventional time inversion.

The dual field tensor $G^{\mu\nu}$ is given by [22]:

$$G^{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -E_z & +E_y & -cB_x \\ +E_z & 0 & -E_x & -cB_y \\ -E_y & +E_x & 0 & -cB_z \\ +cB_x & +cB_y & +cB_z & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

The transformation between $F_{\mu\nu}$ and $G^{\mu\nu}$ is precisely the field transformation for the time inversion proposed in this paper¹². The covariant components, $G_{\mu\nu}$:

$$G_{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -E_z & +E_y & +cB_x \\ +E_z & 0 & -E_x & +cB_y \\ -E_y & +E_x & 0 & +cB_z \\ -cB_x & -cB_y & -cB_z & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Appendix IV: Further comments on energy

At first glance, the statement that classical electromagnetism is not time-invariant might seem to contradict the energy conservation law, since the latter precisely means the *invariance* of natural laws *in time*. The time-invariance implied by energy conservation, though, is equivalent to the homogeneity of time, (instant by instant, all are identical), but not to its *isotropy* (direction by direction, may be not).

The dichotomy between homogeneity and anisotropy of Time appears, at least, in one instant of Time: the Big Bang (when dealing with the Time's arrow, sooner or later you bump inevitably into its origin). That is an accepted singularity, where Time is not homogeneous. Should, then, the Big Bang be excluded from energy conservation? How to combine the Time's homogeneity for positive time, with the Time's singularity at the Big Bang?

This question of how the Big Bang fits into the energy conservation law is far beyond the scope of this paper, but at least we need to justify the idea that both the homogeneity and the anisotropy of Time are not incompatible (or say, the non-time invariance of Electromagnetism proposed in this paper does not contradict the energy conservation law).

In section 3.2.1, two identical waves (except for the handedness) arose at both sides of the time border, hence carrying opposite energies in each time direction. This result is compatible with the energy conservation principle, if "refined" with the specification of a value (zero) for the net energy of the Universe, in the same way that it was done with

¹² This paper's time-inversion, in SI units, $\mathbf{E} \xrightarrow{\mathbf{T}} c\mathbf{B}$

the charge of the Universe in section 2. Thus, the *energy conservation* law (the energy of the Universe is constant), would become the *energy neutrality* of the Universe, (such a constant should be zero). In agreement with this, a possible energy model for a time singularity is displayed versus time in figure 5. At the time-border, energy exits (source-type border, figure 5.a), —or enters, sink-type border, figure 5.b—, towards —or from— the two directions of Time. The energy is constant for each direction of time independently, (E_+ , for any instant *after* the Time's border, and E_- for any instant *before* it, hence the homogeneity of Time observed for positive time), and, in virtue of energy neutrality, both cancel each other out:

$$E_+ + E_- = 0 \quad \rightarrow \quad E_+ = -E_-$$

This means that energy neutrality requires that the energy travelling forwards in time *must* be opposite (*different*) to that travelling backwards (hence the *anisotropy* of Time at the time border).

Note that time borders, in this paper, are presented as exceptional, singular points, which, however, are compatible with natural laws (Time is singular, but natural laws are not). This is a significant difference with the conventional view of the Big Bang, which is commonly taken as the singular instant where Time starts (there was *nothing* before, neither Time nor natural laws, i.e., a moment of (absolute) “creation”, as we could call it). The solution in this paper suggests a different time border concept, not as a “moment of creation” (or “destruction”), but as a moment of transformation, precisely a consequence of the symmetry of natural laws in time.

Obviously, this is the simplest model: one instant's singularity and a perfectly homogeneous time afterwards. But the admission of energy neutrality for one instant makes it possible for other instants too. Figure 5.c, for instance, shows a not so neat time border.

Figure 5: Energy versus time, (simplified model, one-instant singularity). a) Source-type time singularity. b) Sink-type singularity. c) Broad singularity (in grey, the singularity region).

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